

TREASURE

D6.4: Validation of pilot plants circularity level (ORDP)

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Technical References

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document has been elaborated to provide all the necessary information to replicate the calculations conducted in the deliverable D6.4, regarding the validation of circularity of the three pilot plants developed in TREASURE project. Although the information relating the data used is included in this document, the procedure applied has been already explained in the deliverable.

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1. Introduction

The indicators applied for validating the circularity are thermodynamic rarity and intrinsic economic value. Thermodynamic rarity is obtained by multiplying the mass of metals in a given component by a conversion factor, while intrinsic economic value is calculated based on the mass of metals multiplied by their market value. The conversion factor and the market values are shown below.

Table 1. Thermodynamic Rarity values [kJ/g].

Ag	8,937	Ge	24,247	Ru	2,870,013
Al	661	Hf	32,364	Sb	487.9
As	427	Hg	28,707	Sm	732
Au	654,683	In	363,918	Sn	452
Ba	39.34	Ir	2,870,013	Sr	76.39
Be	709.9	La	336	Ta	485,911
Bi	545.6	Li	978	Tb	732
Cd	6,440	Mg	145.7	Te	2,825,104
Ce	620	Mn	73	Ti	203
Co	11,010	Mo	1,056	U	1,090
Cr	40.9	Nb	4,782	V	1,572
Cu	348.4	Nd	670	W	8,023
Dy	732	Ni	758	Y	1,357
Er	732	Pb	41	Yb	732
Eu	732	Pd	2,870,013	Zn	196
Fe	32	Pr	873	Zr	2,025
Ga	754,828	Pt	2,870,013	PC	70
Gd	4,085	Rh	103,087		

Table 2. Price used for the intrinsic economic value.

Metal	€/ton	Metal	€/ton	Metal	€/ton	Metal	€/ton	Metal	€/ton
Ag	664,604	Bi	8,386	Fe	112	Ni	31,577	Sn	30,972
Al	2,751	Ca	579	In	208,640	Pb	1,962	Sr	1,910
As	929	Cd	2,539	Mg	5,132	Pd	72,858,398	Ta	152,469
Au	55,196,821	Co	60,259	Mn	4	Pt	29,777,300	Ti	12,313
B	916	Cr	2,065	Mo	38,318	Ru	16,355,140	V	20,192
Ba	444	Cu	8,355	Nb	42,056	Sb	11,228	W	311
Be	834,841	Dy	211,729	Nd	155,134	Si	2,133	Zn	3,362

Table 3. Intrinsic economic values of the different materials subjected to the hydrometallurgical recycling processes.

Material	Intrinsic Economic Value, €/kg
In-mold electronics	7.25
Printed circuit boards of combi-meter	9.05
ITO glass of LCDs	0.55

2. Information of the pilots

2.1. Semi-automated PCB disassembly pilot

In this section it is added the relevant information conducted to validate the collaborative robot. As a case study has been selected a combi-instrument. It is possible to find the composition of this component below.

Table 4. Mass composition of the combi-instrument

metal	g	metal	g	metal	g	metal	g	metal	g
Ag	0.810	Bi	0.003	Fe	7.029	Ni	0.373	Sn	5.545
Al	13.783	Ca	0.432	In	0.011	Pb	0.121	Sr	0.975
As	0.000	Cd	3.00E-07	Mg	0.273	Pd	4.99E-07	Ta	0.510
Au	0.559	Co	1.23E-06	Mn	0.023	Pt	0.015	Ti	1.622
B	0.414	Cr	0.107	Mo	0.019	Ru	1.97E-06	V	0.001
Ba	1.332	Cu	18.769	Nb	0.007	Sb	2.650	W	9.00E-05
Be	2.04E-10	Dy	0.057	Nd	0.835	Si	7.368	Zn	0.206

Table 5. Recycling rates applied [%]

Ag	85	Bi	0	Fe	0	Mn	0	REE (Dy+Nd)	0
Al	0	Ca	0	Ga	0	Ni	95	Sb	0
Au	95	Co	95	In	0	Pb	95	Sn	75
B	0	Cr	0	Li	0	Pd	95	Ta	100
Ba	0	Cu	95	Mg	0	Pt	95	Zn	65

The next table shows the recyclability and disassembly time (and cost) for every case:

Table 6. Data applied in every case analysed.

	Recycl. [%]		Min		€
Case 1: Shredding	0.03	Shredding time (min)	0	Shredding cost	0.00
Case 2: Car dismantling	59.09	Car dismantling time	9	Car dismantling cost	6.10
Case 3: Part-disassembly	58.55	Part-disassembly time	14	Part-disassembly cost	9.49
Case 4: Cobot	94.54	Case 4: Cobot time	15.48	Case 4: Cobot cost	9.59

2.2. Hydrometallurgical materials recycling pilot

The following information has been applied for the calculation of the indicators of the two routes carried out.

2.2.1. Recycling of indium-tin oxide glass from LCDS (In recovery)

Description of the process

The developed hydrometallurgical process aimed at selectively recovering indium from **indium-tin-oxide glass** (ITO glass) of liquid crystal displays (LCDs) according to a **minimal liquid discharge (MLD) approach**.

The ITO glass is preliminary washed with water to remove liquid crystals. This step is crucial to prevent any negative impact on the recovery stage of indium from the leach liquor. The water can be reused for washing up to 5 times before being discharged to the wastewater treatment section.

To dissolve indium, the cleaned ITO glass underwent a **multistage counter-current leaching** (solid-liquid extraction) process. It consists of three steps using a leaching solution of sulfuric acid (0.1 mol/L) that must be performed at 60 °C. Fresh leaching solution enters from one side (third step), and fresh solid (ITO glass) enters from the opposite side. The main advantages are a more efficient use of reagents and highly concentrated leach liquor from each it is easier to recover the indium.

Electrodeposition occurs at the following operative conditions: voltage = 2.5 V, current density 50 A/m², graphite as cathode material, and titanium coated by a mixed oxide as anode. **The indium metal powder has been recovered with a purity of 99.3%**; impurities are due to tin, and calcium sulfate.

By increasing the free acidity after electrodeposition, you can recycle up to 80% of the solution discharged from indium. This recycling can be done in the counter-current leaching section, with partial sulfuric acid make-up (50%). This approach not only reduces waste and environmental impact but also saves costs leading to a more sustainable and profitable process. The remaining 20% of the solution and the water used to wash the ITO glass are sent to the wastewater section.

The wastewater treatment process involves a stage where lime (10%) is added to neutralize the solution and transfer the pollutants in the sludges. This results in a water quality that meets the standard for direct discharge to sewerage at low costs. Additionally, the treated water can be reused within the plant if necessary.

Water consumption of the process is 1960.3 kg per 1 ton of ITO glass, resulting in a water footprint of 1440.5 kg of water/kg indium product.

Description of the used equipment

Chemical reactor (R102): this chemical reactor is like a slurry reactor; the agitator reaches almost the bottom of the reactor, ensuring good mixing. This kind of reactor is used to prepare the leaching solution. The useful volume is 100 liters, and the construction material is PP.

Chemical reactor (R103): this chemical reactor is used for counter-current leaching operations. ITO glass was prepared in pieces of 2x2 cm. During the leaching process, hot water is sent to the reactor via a boiler, and the solution is heated up to 60°C using a coil placed inside the reactor.

The reactor capacity is 100 liters, and the construction material is PP. Inside the reactor, almost to the bottom, is located a septum with several openings of 1.2 mm that allow the passage of the solution but not of the solid. During the filtration, the septum retains most of the solid, while only small particles detached from the solid during the leaching cross the septum are retained by a cartridge filter.

Pumps: pneumatic diaphragm pumps serve the two chemical reactors to transfer the solutions. Centrifugal pumps are used for chemical loading.

Filters: filtration occurs by using a cartridge filter. It consists of the forced passage of the solution through a porous nylon medium with openings of 10 µm.

Electrolysis cell (CE102): it is used to recover silver from the leach liquor. It is constituted by a bath of 20 liters and equipped with one silver/copper cathode and two titanium coated by mixed oxide anodes. The rectifier allows voltage/current regulation and a centrifugal pump aimed at recirculating the solution.

The plant is equipped with controllers, automatic valves, and programmable logic controller (PLC) software.

Overall inputs and outputs of the process

Table 7. Inputs and outputs of the process.

INPUTS:	OUTPUTS:
ITO glass 1000 kg	secondary product (glass) 938 kg
freshwater 1960.3 kg	humidity 93.9 kg
sulfuric acid (50%) 79.9 kg	indium powder 1.3 kg
lime (10%) 109.5 kg	treated water to sewerage 1824.2 kg
	wet sludges (calcium sulfate) 292.3 kg

Efficiency of the process (extraction yield and purity of the final product)

Table 8. Product obtained and efficiency of the equipment.

Product	EQUIPMENT EFFICIENCIES:
indium recovery 98.7%	R102 (leaching operation) In recovery 99.5%
final product (indium powder): In 99.3%, Sn 0.58%, CaSO ₄ 0.12%	CE102 (electrodeposition operation) In recovery 99.2%

Amount of metal input/output (per 1 ton of ITO glass)

- In metal input: 1324 g
- In metal output in the final product: 1307 g
- In metal not recovered: 17 g

2.2.2. Recycling of in-mold structural electronics (Ag recovery)

Description of the process

The developed hydrometallurgical process aimed at recovering silver from **in-mold structural electronics (IMSEs)** according to a **minimal liquid discharge (MLD) approach**.

The hydrometallurgical process includes a **two-step leaching** (solid-liquid extraction) for the dissolution of silver and the subsequent recovery of silver from the solution by **electrodeposition**. The leaching solution is composed of thiourea (20 g/L) and ferric sulfate (6 g/L as Fe^{3+}) in a sulfuric acid media (0.2 mol/L). The second step of leaching is conducted by reusing the liquor solution obtained by the first step with a make-up of chemicals based on the amount that has been consumed, measured by titration. Electrodeposition occurs at the following operative conditions: voltage = 1.2 V, current density 50 A/m², silver as cathode material, and titanium coated by a mixed oxide as anode. **The silver metal powder has been recovered with a purity of 98.6%**; impurities are due to iron, copper, and calcium sulfate.

The discharged silver solution is not wasted, but rather, it can be reused in a new cycle of the process, promoting a sustainable approach. This is made possible by the partial regeneration of thiourea and the increase of free acidity during the electrowinning, with a make-up of chemicals. The process can be conducted in this way for three cycles, significantly reducing the water footprint.

The **wastewater treatment section** is a crucial part of our process, ensuring that the water used is treated to the highest standards. It includes a Fenton treatment to decompose organic substances, and a lime treatment for an overall reduction of COD of 94% and of iron that exceeds 99%. This ensures that the water obtained from the wastewater treatment section is of high quality, with 70% of it being reused in a new batch of the hydrometallurgical process, and the rest being discharged in sewerage as the COD and metal content are below the required limits.

This way, **water consumption was reduced to 464 kg to treat 1 ton of IMSEs**. The water footprint equals 60.3 kg of water/kg silver product.

Description of the used equipment

Chemical reactor (R102): this chemical reactor is like a slurry reactor; the agitator reaches almost the bottom of the reactor, ensuring good mixing. This kind of reactor is used to prepare the leaching solution. The useful volume is 100 liters, and the construction material is PP.

Chemical reactor (R103): this chemical reactor is used for leaching operations and is intended for treating a solid without any size reduction. The capacity is 100 liters, and the construction material is PP. Inside the reactor, almost to the bottom, is located a septum with several openings of 1.2 mm that allow the passage of the solution but not of the solid. During the filtration, the septum retains most of the solid, while only small particles detached from the solid during the leaching cross the septum are retained by a cartridge filter.

Pumps: pneumatic diaphragm pumps serve the two chemical reactors to transfer the solutions. Centrifugal pumps are used for chemical loading.

Filters: filtration occurs by using a cartridge filter. It consists of the forced passage of the solution through a porous nylon medium with openings of 10 μm .

Electrolysis cell (CE102): it is used to recover silver from the leach liquor. It is constituted by a bath of 20 liters and equipped with one silver/copper cathode and two titanium coated by mixed oxide anodes. The rectifier allows voltage/current regulation and a centrifugal pump aimed at recirculating the solution.

The plant is equipped with controllers, automatic valves, and programmable logic controller (PLC) software.

Overall inputs and outputs of the process

Table 9. Inputs and outputs of the process.

INPUTS:	OUTPUTS:
in-mold structural electronics 1000 kg	secondary product (polycarbonate) 984 kg
fresh water 464.3 kg	humidity 47.2 kg
thiourea 130.7 kg	silver powder 7.7 kg
ferric sulphate 449.6 kg	treated water to sewerage 1189 kg
sulfuric acid (50%) 131.5 kg	wet sludges (calcium and ferrous sulfate) 667 kg

Efficiency of the process (extraction yield and purity of the final product)

Table 10. Product obtained and efficiency of the equipment.

Product	EQUIPMENT EFFICIENCIES:
silver recovery 82.9%	R102 (leaching operation) Ag recovery 84.2%
final product (silver powder): Ag 98.6%, CaSO ₄ 1.07%, Fe 0.26%, Cu 0.10%.	CE102 (electrodeposition operation) Ag recovery 98.5%

Amount of metal input/output

- Ag metal input: 9.3 kg
- Ag metal output in the final product: 7.7 kg
- Ag metal not recovered. 1.6 kg

2.3. IME eco-design and prototyping pilot

The circularity in the third pilot plant, based on the manufacture of in-mold electronics, has been assessed by comparing the technology developed by TNO (IME) with a traditional part from a SEAT vehicle. The comparison has been conducted based on the material composition of both components. However, the material compositions of both components contain sensitive information for both TNO and SEAT. Therefore, it is not possible to provide further details regarding the calculation of the circularity of this pilot plant.

3. Other information

As previously mentioned, this document includes all the relevant data needed to replicate all the calculations (except for the sensitive data). However, it must be noted again that the information related to the procedures and the steps followed have been included in D6.4.